

Bats and rabies: quiescence and virus replication

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Abstract

Rabies, a fatal neurological infectious disease, etiologically linked to a member of the *Lyssavirus* genus within the *Rhabdoviridae* family, the Rabies Virus, is mainly transmitted to man and domestic animals by bites, scratches and licking of infected animals, as stray dogs and cats, bats and other wild animals. Bats, in the order Chiroptera, represent one of the largest groups of mammals in the Planet. These flying mammals play an extraordinary and vital role in the ecosystem, but anthropic behavior disrupts the ecosystem harmony, spreading diseases transmitted by bats, eventually of significant impact on human and animal health. Outbreaks of viral diseases, transmitted by bats, have frequently occurred all around the world. The bat's immune system mechanisms that maintain virions and/or viral gene sequences/genomes dormant/quiescent, and factors that activate virus replication and/or viral genome set up to produce virion progeny capable to infect other hosts, is not well understood. In this review, based on the data of some laboratories, it is discussed possible mechanisms and factors involved in virus latency and activation in bats. Certainly, the interaction of bioorganisms, at different levels of quantitative and qualitative complexity, determines the outputs of epidemiological events of distinct magnitudes, but also factors that affect the planet as a whole, like the solar geomagnetic disturbance, has a profound impact in the extent of chiropterans' performance in nature, if not, the determinant factor in the settings of the space weather.

1. Introduction

Rabies virus (RABV), a zoonotic pathogen, is among the scariest etiological agent of a quite lethal neurological disease, generally of very low incidence. In urban areas, immunization of pets has significantly reduced RABV infection and disease. Anyway, stray domestic animals, commonly found in low-income countries, are a major problem to avoid the virus circulation, so the incidence of rabies, in man and pets, depends on the public health policies closely linked to the socioeconomic status of its population (1-3). Besides, unplanned land occupation concurrently with environmental disturbance, displacing wild animals from their roosting and feeding areas, remarkably impacts rabies statistics among husbandry animals. Due to the dietary habits, bats, mainly the hematophagous *Desmodus rotundus*, are a major concern of RABV transmission, even though viral antigens/gene sequences have been detected in tissues of carnivorous, omnivorous and insectivorous bat species (4-6). Apart from *Desmodus rotundus*, well-known for feeding on blood of cattle, pigs, horses and other homeothermic vertebrates, there are other hematophagous species that rely, mainly, on birds' blood for meals as *Diaemus youngi* and *Diphylla ecaudata* (4-7).

The close etiological association of hematophagous bats and RABV infection, and the resulting outbreaks of rabies among domestic animals preyed by bats, does not display a comprehensible pattern (7,8). Data, of many authors, suggest that all bat species are susceptible to RABV infection, and eventually carry RABV in their brain neurons and salivary glands, notwithstanding, it is not known if the most common RABV transmitter, *Desmodus rotundus*, has in its genome, transcriptionally silent cognate viral genes (5-10). If bat individuals carry or are infected by the virus, which conditions do favor or impair disease development? Do they transmit the virus during silent viral gene transcription, if does it occur? or can they control virus replication and down regulate the viral pathogenicity?

2. RABV General Features

RABV is taxonomically positioned in the genus *Lyssavirus*, family *Rhabdoviridae*. Its ~12 kb RNA single genome is non segmented and of negative polarity. It encodes the structural proteins of the nucleocapsid (N), the phosphoprotein (P), the matrix (M), the glycoprotein (G) and the viral RNA polymerase (L). The virion displays a lipoprotein envelope, acquired from the host cell membrane, which expresses glycosylated proteins. The nucleocapsid, surrounded by the viral

envelope, encapsidates the viral helical RNA, that shapes the virion bullet morphology with an average diameter of 85 nm X 178 nm length (11,12).

3. Virus' Cell Interaction and Neuropathology

RABV is neurotropic, and after its usual transmission by the combination of salivary bites and scratches of infected animals, inoculated virus, in the muscle tissue, interacts its trimeric G spikes protein with host cell receptors in the muscular form of nicotinic acetylcholine receptor, and with other receptors in neurocytes as the neuronal cell adhesion molecule and the p75 neurotrophin receptor (13). Even though host cells support low levels of RABV replication, it is sufficient viral cargo to migrate through peripheral nerves to the encephalon, most probably by synaptic connections as the amount of RABV genes are more expressed in neurocytes than in other cells (14). Its full replication, in neuronal cells and astrocytes, results in encephalomyelitis, the inflammation of the central nervous tissues. Quantitation of the gene copy number of RABV, in the brain of six rabid bovines, yielded more nucleotide sequences' amplification in the cortex, medulla and thalamus (15). The virus circumvents the host innate immune response through its M and P proteins evasion of the NF- κ B and JAK-STAT host cell pathways. Besides, RABV infection of Schwann cells, in the peripheral nerves, depresses glial cells mediated immunity and retards the antiviral response. Neuronal dysfunction rather than neurological death better explains the minimal pathological changes observed in the brains of deceased hosts. Neurological damage would result from abnormal mitochondrial bioenergetics and cristae architecture, that altogether induce mitophagy, and ultimately autophagy, leading invariably to lethal outcomes (16-20). A pathognomonic sign of rabies infection was described by Aldechi Negri in 1903, as inclusion bodies in the cytoplasm of RABV infected neurocytes. Despite debates on the diagnostic values of these bodies' detection, Negri's wife, Lina Negri-Luzzani confirmed the relationship between RABV infection and inclusion bodies development. Later, Negri's corpuscles was denominated in his honor (21). Negri's couple findings opened new avenues to unravel the significance of these inclusion bodies as viral factories, microenvironments in the cell cytoplasm to protect the viral genome and to sustain the mechanisms of virus replication, viral protein synthesis and processing as also, virion assembly (21). Negri inclusions detection is a classical method to diagnostic RABV infection utilizing the Seller's staining histological technique (21-24).

4. Epidemiology: Preventive and Control Measures of RABV infection

Despite the availability of preventive measures to RABV infection, as the use of vaccine and anti-rabies hyperimmune serum, global epidemiologic surveillance points out to 50,000 to 60,000 human deaths annually, particularly in developing countries in African, Asian and Latin American, mainly among children of low socioeconomic income families (3,14,15). Nowadays, preventive measures to RABV infection target pets and domestic animals, but wild animals go far beyond any control (2,6,9). Along with health education, recommended common procedures, after bites, scratches and licking by unknown animals, usually dogs and cats, and rarely bats or other wild animals, stand the washing of the lesions with soap to remove the lipidic virion envelope, and keeping the cleaning area exposed to the air. Also, serotherapy should be administered to neutralize, by anti-RABV specific immunoglobulins, possible tissue inoculated virions. RABV immunization is preconized to animal health professionals as veterinarians, animal handlers, laboratory workers in rabies diagnostic and research, etc (25,26).

Of economic importance, rabies has imposed losses to the livestock farming. In the period of 1970-2030, South America northern countries experienced 450 rabies epidemics by year, in average, dying at least 6 cattle in each event. Despite efforts to prevent RABV infection as immunization of farming animals and control of hematophagous bats feeding on these animals, cattle management is very heterogenous, encompassing large areas, sometimes of difficult access (27).

5. RABV as an Agent of Population Control

Here, it is raised the hypothesis that wild animals' population control can be exerted by infectious agent, as exemplified and reflected by outbreaks of RABV in the branch of animal husbandry, mainly transmitted by hematophagous bats. Selectively concerning bats' colonies, a plethora of factors can disturb the population harmony, so the overcrowd of these flying mammals, in their habits, eventually ignites hormone production, glucocorticoids and catecholamines, leading to bat stress and resulting immunosuppression, and the expression of infectious agents and disease, that in the long run results in death incidence, contributing to the control of population density which benefits surviving animals for adequate space and food availability (28-30). Man's

interference, in the ecosystem of wild animals, is of paramount importance, e.g., deforestation of natural environments deprive them of their habitats and food/water supplies, as also, the artisanal precious mineral exploitation with the employment of mercury, contaminates natural water courses and soil, spreading the organic form of mercury, methylmercury, by plants and animals, so its ingestion, by bats and other wild animals, can result in the depression of the immune system (31-33), that besides the incidence of infectious diseases, would allow the expression of dormant or endogenous viral genes (30,34-37). Furthermore, other heavy metals contaminants, such as cadmium and lead, derived from anthropic activity, have detrimental role in the health of bats as also of other wild and domestic animals (38-40). Besides controllable factors, as those dependable on human activity, nature per se, has the most striking influence on the physiology of all living things, as the solar geomagnetic activity (41). Some studies have linked the peaks of solar activity to epidemic and pandemic events, as the epidemiological events protagonized by the influenza virus and other infectious agents (41-43).

6. Conclusion

Population dynamics of living beings are composed of an interactive net of organisms in different levels of complexity, for instance, mammal's species are highly associated to prokaryotic organisms and viruses (44,45). Human evolution has been implicated in the interference of its domesticated animals and plants' ecosystems as also in the wild life. The environment disturbance authored by man, known as the anthropization, triggered off disequilibrium in the population dynamics of many organisms, particularly concerning to chiropterans. It has been corroborated, by many studies, that these flying mammals harbor a vast array of microorganisms' genomes or genetic sequences, mostly viruses, which has been implicated in life threatening epidemiological events of animal and human significance (46,47). Despite bats' involvement in the elevated incidence of morbidity and mortality by viruses, apparently bats have the capacity to control and/or to repress their replication, possibly explained by the bats' accelerated rate metabolism. Anyway, it is here reinforced the role played by man in the outburst of infectious diseases biologically vectorized by wild animals, in special, by bats.

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